

GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource:

Checklist for responsible research assessment

Actionable version

Definition

The checklist is a self-evaluation tool designed to help universities and research organisations ensure their assessment practices align with principles of fairness, transparency, diversity, and accountability. It covers the full cycle of academic and research career assessment: from planning and conducting evaluations to reflecting and improving future processes.

Relevant SCOPE stages

The checklist supports all five SCOPE stages:

- S – Start with what you value: Ground assessments in institutional mission, strategy, and shared values.
- C – Context considerations: Why are you evaluating and who you are evaluating (e.g., entity size and discipline).
- O – Options for evaluating: Choose diverse methods and indicators, balancing qualitative judgement with responsible use of metrics.
- P – Probe deeply: Consider potential discrimination, gaming of the approach, unintended consequences, and weigh the cost-benefit.
- E – Evaluate your evaluation: Reflect on lessons learned, document decisions, and improve future assessments.

When and how to use

When:

- At all stages of designing, running, and reviewing academic career or research assessment exercises.

How:

- Use as a planning tool when setting up evaluation criteria, methods, and teams.
- Apply as a checklist during implementation to ensure fairness and compliance.
- Deploy as a reflection framework after completion for learning and improvement.

Who should use it:

- HR professionals, evaluators, institutional leaders, and researchers involved in assessment.

Guidance

1. Building the assessment process

- Define values, purposes, objectives, and criteria openly and ensure aligning with relevant RRA reform initiatives (e.g., CoARA).
- Ensure that evaluators are competent, diverse, trained, and free of conflicts of interest.
- Provide clear instructions, transparent guidelines, and fair data practices (including consent and GDPR compliance).

2. Assessing contributions to knowledge

- Prioritise qualitative judgement; use metrics responsibly and only with relevant expertise.
- Avoid reliance on Journal Impact Factor, h-index, or university rankings.
- Enable assessed individuals to review and verify data used.

3. Recognising diverse outputs and activities

- Value a broad range of contributions: publications, datasets, methods, teaching, supervision, leadership, societal interaction, and open science practices.
- Consider career stage, discipline-specific contexts, and different types of opportunities available.

4. After the assessment

- Communicate progress and outcomes clearly to all parties.
- Provide constructive feedback and channels for raising concerns.
- Safeguard sensitive documents and ensure GDPR compliance.

5. Evaluating the assessment process

- Document decisions and reasoning throughout.
- Actively gather feedback from all parties.
- Share lessons learned for continuous improvement across institutions.

Further reading

- SCOPE Framework (INORMS, 2023): <https://doi.org/10.26188/21919527.v1>
- Open Science Coordination in Finland, Federation of Finnish Learned Societies (2022): Self-Evaluation Tool For Culture Of Open Scholarship Services. [DOI:10.23847/tsv.447](https://doi.org/10.23847/tsv.447)